

Equilibrium and Kinetic Studies of the Acid-Base Reaction between Carbinol Base of Crystal Violet and Acids in Benzene

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The slow reaction in benzene between the colourless carbinol base of crystal violet and eleven different acids to produce the coloured salt has been investigated with respect to equilibrium and kinetics. The equilibrium constant, K_a is of the form, $K_a = \frac{(\text{Dye Salt})}{(\text{Dye Base})(\text{Acid})^n}$ where n in all cases is found to be greater than unity. Phenol and the Lewis acid, HgCl_2 behave as unexpectedly strong acids. The relative protonation power of the acids is thus found to depend strongly on the specific protonation reaction employed and on the solvent. Possible reasons for the acid exponent being higher than unity have been discussed.

Kinetic studies indicate that the overall reaction is a reversible first order reaction, both the rates of the forward and the backward reactions being influenced by acid. The rate constants and the acid exponents for both the forward and the reverse reaction have been calculated. The acid exponent for the reverse reaction is found to be negative signifying that acids retard the reverse reaction which is suggested to be due to complex formation between the acid and the dye salt. A Hammett-type relation is found to exist for the aromatic acids for both equilibrium and kinetic constants, if $\text{p}K_a$ values in water are used as reference.

There are but a few systematic and reliable investigations regarding acid-base reactions involving dyes in organic solvents. Outstanding among these are that of Kolthoff and Brukenstein¹ in acetic acid medium, LaMer and Downes² in benzene medium and the recent extensive work of Davis and co-workers³⁻⁵ and Popovych⁶ in aprotic solvents for the determination of base strength using an indicator as the reference acid. Benzene medium has received little attention in this type of work; this is probably due to the fact that most of the cationic dyes are insoluble or sparingly soluble in benzene. The difficulty can be easily got over by extracting the dye (presumably the dye base) from an alkaline dye solution by benzene,—a technique^{10,11} recently developed in this laboratory. The present work utilizes the above technique to prepare the carbinol base of crystal violet in benzene and reports the results of both equilibrium studies and kinetic studies of the reaction between the carbinol base and eleven acids including HgCl_2 , a Lewis acid.

1. Kolthoff and Brückenstein, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1, 10.
2. LaMer and Downes, *ibid.*, 1933, 55, 1840.
3. Davis and Schuhmann, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1947, 39, 221.
4. Davis and McDonald, *ibid.*, 1949, 42, 595.
5. Davis and Hetzer, *ibid.*, 1951, 46, 496.
6. Davis and Hetzer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 4247.
7. Davis and Hetzer, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1960, 64, 659.
8. Davis and Paabo, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 3081.
9. Popovych, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 915.
10. Palit, *Anal. Chem.*, 1961, 33, 1441.
11. Palit, *Chem. and Ind. (London)* 1960, 1531.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Dry distilled high grade benzene stored over sodium wire was used. The acids were of high grade (in some cases recrystallised), and fresh solutions of vacuum-dried samples in benzene were immediately standardised and used. Crystal violet (E. Merck, for microscopy and non-aqueous titration), twice recrystallised from methanol-benzene mixture, was used. The carbinol base of crystal violet was prepared as follows: About 15 mg of the dye was precipitated from water as carbinol base by sodium hydroxide (about 2*N*). The whole was then extracted with about 200 ml of benzene, and the benzene extract (which slowly changes from yellow to the stable colourless carbinol form) was stored airtight in dark over metallic sodium wire and was used as required.

Procedure.—Optical measurements were recorded at 610 m μ for all benzene solutions from a Hilger UVSPECK Spectrophotometer using 1-cm stoppered silica cells, the temperature of which was regulated by an accessory device to $\pm 0.2^\circ$. Error due to plating of the cell surface by the dye was avoided by plating out both the sample and the reference solution cells before the commencement of the actual measurements.

Dilution of the stock solutions of acid and carbinol base was made in a small chamber saturated with benzene vapour, thus minimising the error due to evaporation. The concentration range for carbinol base was from 5×10^{-6} to 10^{-3} moles/litre and those of acids were so adjusted as to bring about 25% to 75% conversion of the dye into the coloured salt. Optical density measurements were made at $20^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ after attainment of equilibrium (half to one hour). The indicator ratio, $[DH^+A^-]/[D]$ was calculated from the relation $x_e/b-x_e$, where x_e = concentration of the coloured salt at equilibrium in terms of optical density, b = total concentration of the carbinol base in terms of the same unit. (The latter is obtained by complete conversion of the carbinol base into coloured form on shaking with sufficient amount of benzoic acid so that further addition of the acid brought no more change in colour. Benzoic acid was preferably chosen for such measurements because the spectral maximum was found to be independent of the composition of the solution in presence of this acid).

The total concentration of the indicator base in terms of molar concentration could be determined by shaking the carbinol base with aqueous H_2SO_4 solution ($3 \times 10^{-3}N$) and extracting the whole amount of dye in aqueous layer and determining its concentration from the calibration curve (Beers Law). Any intermediate optical density reading could be converted to molar concentration from the extinction coefficient ($\epsilon = 8.541 \times 10^4$ cm $^{-1}$ litre/mole) of crystal violet in benzene at 25° .

Kinetic Experiments—The rate of reactions between carbinol base and different acids was followed spectrophotometrically at $20^\circ \pm 0.2^\circ$ by recording the optical density values at suitable time intervals until the equilibrium value was attained (usually less than one hour). Generally two sets of experiments were performed; in one, the concentration of acid was fixed, while in the other, the acid concentration was varied.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I EQUILIBRIUM STUDIES

Calculation of Equilibrium Constant—It is found from our experimental

results that if the equilibrium constant, K_a is calculated according to the equation,

$$\therefore K_a = \frac{[\text{D}^+\text{A}^-] \times [\text{H}_2\text{O}]}{[\text{DOH}] \times [\text{HA}]} \quad \dots (2)$$

(where DOH is the dye carbinol base and HA, the added acid), its value increases very rapidly with increase in acid concentration. This is perhaps one of the reasons why little systematic data are available regarding such studies in benzene medium. We were however rather surprised to find that K_a is constant at particular acid concentration only if the liberation of water is ignored in eqn.2. Therefore, it is believed that most probably the water molecule formed in eqn. 1 is associated with any one of the species present in the system through hydrogen bond and they exist as one entity. Such association in organic solvents is not uncommon; for example, Tuck and Diamond¹² report that hydrogen ion, H_3O^+ exists as $\text{H}_3\text{O}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n^+$ in solvent extraction of strong acids by basic solvents. Similar association between water and carboxylic acids (RCOOH , H_2O) is also indicated by Christian et al¹³. So the reaction between carbinol base of crystal violet and an acid may be represented as

and since the fate of water is unknown, we write the above equilibrium as

where the association constant is given by

$$K_a = \frac{[\text{DH}^+\text{A}^-]}{[\text{D}] [\text{HA}]} \quad \dots (5)$$

(i) *Variation of Dye Concentration.*—The values of K_a are constant within experimental error, when the concentration of carbinol base is varied at fixed acid concentration. This is illustrated for benzoic acid ($[\text{Acid}] = 1.63 \times 10^{-2} \text{M}$) at 20° in the following table where the indicator ratio, (coloured form)/(colourless form) is fairly constant, though the carbinol base concentration is changed by a factor of two. The same is the case with other acids.

$[\text{Dye}] \times 10^6$ moles/litre	$\frac{[\text{DH}^+\text{A}^-]}{[\text{D}]}$	$\frac{[\text{Coloured}]}{\text{form}} / \frac{[\text{Colourless}]}{\text{form}}$
6.289	1.27	
6.648	1.25	
9.149	1.36	
12.19	1.34	

12. Tuck and Diamond, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 193.

13. Christian, Affesprung and Taylor, *Ibid.*, 1963, 67, 187.

(ii) *Variation of Acid Concentration.*—However, when the acid concentration is varied eqn. 5 no longer holds good, the value of K_a increasing rapidly with increase in acid concentration. This is clearly indicated by the fact that though we do get linear graphs when $\log [DH^+A^-]/[D]$ vs $-\log [HA]$ are plotted for different acids, the slope is different from unity and varies from acid to acid as shown in Fig. 1. Our results therefore fit well with an empirical formula of the type,

$$K_a = \frac{[DH^+A^-]}{[D][HA]^n} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\therefore \log \frac{[DH^+A^-]}{[D]} = n \log [HA] + \log K_a \quad \dots (7)$$

where the value of n varies from acid to acid, and is obtainable from the slope of the straight line shown in Fig. 1. At 50% salt conversion, $[DH^+A^-] = [D]$ and so we have

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log [DH^+A^-]/[D]$ vs $-\log [HA]$ for the reactions between carbinol base and different acids.

1. Salicylic, 2. Monochloroacetic, 3. *m*-Chlorobenzoic, 4. Mercuric chloride, 5. Phenylacetic, 6. *m*-Methoxybenzoic, 7. Benzoic, 8. Acetic, 9. *m*-Toluic, 10. Butyric, and 11. Phenol.

$$\log K_a = -n \log [HA]_{:1} \quad \dots (8)$$

and equation which is convenient for computation of K_a . Table I gives the summary of results.

Comparison of the Relative Strength of Acids.—Taking K_a as a measure of acid strength in benzene and comparing the same with the corresponding acid strength in water, it is found that the relative change in the acid strength in benzene, is much greater than it is in water; in other words, the pK_a values extend over a longer range (Table I). Thus in aliphatic acids, we see butyric acid which is 1.17 times weaker than acetic acid in water is found to be 10 times weaker than the latter in benzene, and monochloroacetic acid which is about 80 times stronger than acetic acid in water is about 5×10^5 times stronger in benzene.

TABLE I

Values of the equilibrium constant, K_a , the acid exponent n in eqn. 6 and $-\log [HA]_{1:1}$:

Acids	Slope n	$-\log [HA]_{1:1}$ (i.e., 50% salt conversion)	$\log K_a$ (20°C in benzene)	pK_a (25° in water)
Acetic	1.75	1.740	3.005	4.751
Butyric	1.48	1.290	1.905	4.818
Monochloroacetic	2.15	4.050	8.707	2.863
Phenylacetic	1.60	2.295	3.672	4.310
Benzoic	1.64	1.927	3.153	4.213
<i>m</i> -Methoxybenzoic	1.73	2.010	3.454	4.090
<i>m</i> -Toluic	1.55	1.735	2.688	4.270
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic	1.45	3.156	4.574	3.827
Salicylic	1.25	4.560	5.700	2.970
Phenol	3.27	0.985	3.121	9.855
Mercuric chloride	2.10	9.030	6.363	—

In aromatic series taking benzoic acid as standard we find from Table I that *m*-methoxybenzoic acid which is about 1.3 times stronger than benzoic acid in water is only about 2 times stronger in benzene. The same is the case with *m*-toluic acid which is 1.16 times weaker than the benzoic acid in water, is about 2.9 times weaker in benzene. And, *m*-chlorobenzoic acid which is nearly 2.4 times stronger than benzoic acid in aqueous solution is about 26 times stronger in benzene. Thus we find that the relative increase in acidity is not so sharp in these cases as it is in aliphatic series of acids, except for *m*-chlorobenzoic acid. Perhaps this may be the reason why phenylacetic acid which is partly an aromatic acid, is found to be less strong when compared with aliphatic series of acids and more strong when compared with those of aromatic series.

Phenol behaves as an exceptionally strong acid in benzene, being only about 1.1 times (negligible) weaker than benzoic acid as contrasted with its behaviour in water where it is about half a million times weaker. A similar relative enhancement of strength of phenols compared to carboxylic acids was observed by Streuli and Miron¹⁵ in titration studies in pyridine medium.

Chlorinated acids also behave as unexpectedly strong acids in benzene. Thus, in benzene monochloroacetic acid is half a million times stronger than acetic acid; a similar though less marked disparity exists when *m*-chlorobenzoic acid is compared with benzoic acid. Such behaviour may be attributed to some kind of complex formation with benzene leading to an increase of electronegativity of the chlorine atom.

Strength of Mercuric Chloride (Lewis Acid)—The behaviour of $HgCl_2$ is also quite unexpected. It behaves as a very strong acid in benzene medium and one is tempted to think that like hydrogen acids, it can undergo the following reaction to give a coloured salt,

14. Barton and Kraus, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4561.

15. Streuli and Miron, *Anal. Chem.*, 1958, 30, 1978.

An alternative mechanism would be that HgCl_2 draws out an electron from one of the nitrogen atoms of the carbinol base and introduces a positive charge on nitrogen. This latter explanation is more likely because HgCl_2 has been found to produce acid colour in benzene also with the anhydro bases of dyes where there is no OH group.

The Relationship between pK_a in benzene and pK_a in Water.—A fairly good linear Hammett-type relationship exists as is seen from the plot of $\log K_a$ in benzene vs pK_a in water (Fig. 2), for the aromatic acids; the slope being much greater than unity. But the linearity is very poor in the case of aliphatic acids. On the whole, however, this linear relationship may be taken as an approximate one. Even the relative order of K_a in benzene and K_a in water are not the same as is shown in a tabular form below. It is evident that we have yet to find a guiding principle which successfully predicts even qualitatively the order of acid strength in organic solvents.

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log K_a$ in benzene at 20° with pK_a in water at 25° .

1. Acetic acid, 2. Butyric acid, 3. Monochloroacetic acid, 4. Phenylacetic acid, 5. Benzoic acid, 6. *m*-Methoxybenzoic acid, 7. *m*-Toluic acid, 8. *m*-Chlorobenzoic acid, 9. Salicylic acid, 10. Phenol.

Order of acid strength

$-\log (HA)_{5\%}$ (i.e., 50% salt conversion)

Salicylic
> Monochloroacetic
> *m*-Chlorobenzoic
> Mercuric chloride
> Phenylacetic
> *m*-Methoxybenzoic
> Benzoic
> Acetic
> *m*-Toluic
> Butyric
> Phenol

K_a (20° in benzene)

Monochloroacetic
> Salicylic
> Mercuric chloride
> *m*-Chlorobenzoic
> Phenylacetic
> *m*-Methoxybenzoic
> Benzoic
> Phenol
> Acetic
> *m*-Toluic
> Butyric

K_a (25° in water)

Monochloroacetic
Salicylic
—
> *m*-Chlorobenzoic
> *m*-Methoxybenzoic
> Benzoic
> *m*-Toluic
> Phenylacetic
> Acetic
> Butyric
> Phenol

The Value of the Slope n .—The fact that n is not a whole number and is greater than unity needs an explanation. This would probably be related to the well-known fact that most of the carboxylic acids are associated in benzene (for example, the dimerization

constant of benzoic acid¹⁴ in benzene is 6.4×10^4 at 5.4°). The assumption that only the monomeric acid reacts according to eqn. 4 would lead to a value of n less than unity. The explanation is therefore to be sought in other direction. Since acid-anion complexes are well-known to be present in inert media as shown by conductometric¹⁵, potentiometric¹⁷, cryoscopic¹⁸ and infrared studies^{19,20}, the dimer as also the acid-anion complex are also likely to take part in the reaction. This is, made more plausible by the observation of Harlow and Bruss¹⁷ that monobasic and phenolic acids in inert solvents like benzene, toluene, etc. often show two inflections during potentiometric titration, the steeper one being ascribed by them to acid-anion complex, an idea originally due to Maryott¹⁶. This has been corroborated by the potentiometric and conductometric titrations of phenolic compounds in organic solvents by Heijde²¹, Sprangling²², Deal and Eyld²³ and Mitra and Chatterjee²⁴ (or three types of novolaks).

Evidently the situation is very complicated as all the three types of acids present, viz, the monomer, the dimer and the acid-anion complex (and probably polymeric entities in the case of phenol), are capable of taking part in the protonation reaction. The situation is further complicated by the fact that the reverse reaction may also be influenced by the acid. In such case the observed exponent n would be equal to $n=f-r$ where f is the exponent for the forward reaction and r is the exponent for the reverse reaction. The values of f and r have been obtained from kinetic studies.

2. KINETIC STUDIES

Order of reaction with respect to Carbinol Base.—Our experimental data are in accord with the following equation for reversible first order reaction,

$$k = k_1 + k_{-1} = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{x_e}{x_e - x} \quad (9)$$

where x , is the reading in optical density at time, t and x_e , is the reading taken in the same unit at equilibrium; k , is the overall rate constant which is the sum of rate constants k_1 and k_{-1} for the forward and backward reaction respectively. Plots of $-\log(x_e - x)$ versus t at a given acid concentration and at different carbinol base concentrations give very good straight lines parallel to each other for all the acids studied. The values of k were evaluated from the slopes of such plots. Some typical plots are shown in Fig. 3 for benzoic acid. The values of k obtained as above are however found to depend strongly on c , the acid concentration, a non-linear dependency being generally observed. Brønsted and Bell^{25,26} observed a similar dependence in acid-catalysed decomposition of diazonium salts in benzene. Bell attributed such behaviour to association of acid molecules or to medium effect (possibly for the presence of large dipole moments in the acid molecules) analogous to salt effect in aqueous solution.

16. Maryott, *J. Res. Nat. Bur. Stand.*, 1947, **38**, 527.
17. Harlow and Bruss, *Anal. Chem.*, 1958, **30**, 1833, 1836.
18. Kaufman and Singleterry, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1952, **56**, 604.
19. Yergcr and Barrow, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4474, 6206.
20. Barrow, *ibid.*, 1956, **78**, 5902.
21. Vander Heijde, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1957, **16**, 392.
22. Sprangling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 1190.
23. Deal and Eyld, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 47.
24. Mitra and Chatterjee, *J. Sci. and Ind. Res.*, 1961, **20B**, 310.

TABLE II

A typical example showing the kinetic results of benzoic acid

[Dye] $\times 10^6$ moles/litre	[Acid] $\times 10^3$ moles/litre	Slope	$k \text{ min}^{-1}$	k/c
9.072	7.36	0.128	0.290	39.41
9.072	10.74	0.142	0.327	30.44
6.648	14.32	0.171	0.303	27.60
12.190	14.32	0.171	0.393	26.60
9.072	14.32	0.171	0.393	27.60
9.189	17.90	0.182	0.419	23.25
12.170	22.08	0.194	0.446	20.09

Fig. 3. Plots of $\log(x-a)$ vs time for different concentrations of benzoic acid.

Concn. of carbinol base $\times 10^6$ moles/lit	Concn. of acid $\times 10^3$ moles/lit
(1) 9.072	1.074
(2) 6.648	1.432
(3) 9.149	1.790
(4) 12.12	2.208

Fig. 4. Plot of pK_a (water vs. $\log k_1$ for different acids. 1. Acetic, 2. Butyric, 3. Monochloroacetic, 4. Phenyl acetic, 5. Benzoic, 6. *m*-Methoxybenzoic, 7. *m*-Toluic, 8. *m*-Chlorobenzoic, 9. Salicylic, 10. Phenol, 11. Mercuric chloride.

The Individual Rate Constants—Since both equilibrium and kinetic data are available, it is possible to obtain both k_1 and k_{-1} of equation (9). The equilibrium can be formulated in the following way where both the forward and the backward reaction is assumed to be influenced by the acid.

Since the acid is present in various forms it is expected that the acid exponent will not be unity and so, it is set equal to f in the forward and r in the reverse reaction. The following

25. Brønsted and Bell, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 2478.26. Bell, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, A143, 377.

equations are then valid.

$$K_a = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} \frac{[\text{Colored Salt}] [\text{Acid}]^r}{[\text{Carbinol Base}] [\text{Acid}]^f} \quad \dots (11)$$

$$n = f - r \quad \dots (12)$$

$$k = k_1 \text{Acid}^f + k_{-1} (\text{Acid})^r \quad \dots (13)$$

By simple algebraic manipulation these equations yield

$$\frac{k}{K_a + (\text{Acid})^{-n}} = k_{-1} (\text{Acid})^f \quad \dots (14)$$

Thus, by a log-log plot the kinetic constants, k_{-1} and f and therefore all the four kinetic constants, k_1 , k_{-1} , f and r can be obtained. Good linear log-log plots have been actually obtained. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

Acid components and the rate constants for the forward and reverse reactions

Acids	n	f	r	$\log K_a$	$\log k_1$	$\log k_{-1}$
Acetic	1.75	1.55	-0.205	3.005	1.19	-1.81
Butyric	1.48	1.39	-0.084	1.905	0.549	-1.96
Monochloroacetic	2.15	1.69	-0.545	8.707	5.39	-3.32
Phenylacetic	1.60	1.02	-0.585	3.672	1.05	-2.63
Benzoic	1.64	1.19	-0.449	3.153	1.52	-1.64
<i>m</i> -methoxybenzoic	1.73	1.23	-0.498	3.454	1.68	-1.77
<i>m</i> -Toluic	1.55	0.876	-0.674	2.688	0.815	-1.87
<i>m</i> -Chlorobenzoic	1.45	0.819	-0.631	4.574	2.30	-2.27
Salicylic	1.25	0.806	-0.444	5.700	2.41	-3.29
Phenol	3.27	2.28	-0.992	3.121	0.242	-2.88
Mercuric chloride	2.10	1.56	-0.539	6.363	2.373	-3.99

It is already known from the values of K_a (Table 1) that $k_1 > k_{-1}$. The interesting feature is that r comes out to be negative, i.e., the acid retards the reverse reaction of eqn(10). This can be simply interpreted as due to complex formation between the coloured dye salt and the acid which is present in large excess. It is further noted that the value of r is the highest for phenol and is almost equal to unity, i.e. the reverse reaction is inversely proportional to phenol concentration indicating a very stable 1:1 complex formation between the coloured dye salt and phenol. The unexpectedly high protonation power of phenol is contributed only partly by its somewhat high forward rate constant, k_1 , the other contributing factors being a high value of f and a comparatively low rate constant of the reverse reaction. It is thus evident that the overall acid strength in benzene is due to the interplay of at least four factors which are summed up in f , r , k_1 and k_{-1} . If the protonation is done by the monomeric acid alone and if the acid exists almost wholly in the dimeric form, the exponent f should be $\frac{1}{2}$. The observed value of f is always higher and probably is a measure of the departure from the above conditions. Fig 4 shows plot of $\log k_1$ against pK_a in water and the results show that the aromatic acids show a fairly linear correlation. Besides, $\log k_1$ for the four aromatic acids are in the order *m*-chlorg-

benzoic > *m*-methoxy benzoic > benzoic > *m*-toluic which is also the order of Hammett's σ constant for these substituents. Thus the data for the aromatic acids are in fair agreement with Hammett's equation. This might indicate that the rate of ionisation of the acid being a major rate-controlling factor in benzene medium.

Results with mixture of two Acids—The conclusion arrived at from the results with single acids is that the acid (probably all the forms present in the system) plays an important role both in the forward reaction and in the backward reaction; it may also act as a catalyst. In order to confirm whether the reactions were at all catalysed by acid or not, we carried out few experiments with mixtures of acids.

When two different acids are present together, each acid may catalyse the reaction of the other, and this is usually termed as "Cross Catalysis"²³. Thus we should expect a total reaction velocity greater than the sum of velocities for the two acids when present separately at the same concentration, i.e. the values of kinetic increment, Δk ($\Delta k = k_m - k_{HA_1} - k_{HA_2}$) would be positive. Besides, the presence of complex double molecules may cause further increase in velocity. The experimental results are given in Table IV.

The values of Δk in Table IV for the acid mixtures, viz.: acetic acid and benzoic acid; acetic acid and phenylacetic acid are negative. This shows that there is actually a slight reduction in the reaction velocity, that is, cross catalysis does not take place. This reduction is formally similar to the mutual repression of acidity in water when two acids are present together. Our results with the above acid mixtures are similar to those obtained by Brønsted and Bell²⁴ for some acid pairs (dichloroacetic acid and monochloroacetic acid, dichloroacetic acid and α -bromopropionic acid) in the reaction of diazoacetic ester catalysed by acids in benzene medium.

When phenol is present as one of the acids in the mixture, we find that the values of Δk are positive. Thus for acid mixtures, benzoic acid and phenol; phenylacetic acid and phenol; acetic acid and phenol, the values of Δk are positive (Table IV) and they increase with the increase in the product ($C_{HA_1} \cdot C_{HA_2}$) of acid concentration. This indicates that cross catalysis takes place for the above acid pairs. Brønsted and Bell also found that the values of Δk are positive and linear with the product of acid concentration, when one of the acids is phenol in the mixture.

TABLE IV

Acid pair	Range of acid conc. $\times 10^2$ mols/litre	k mixture (min^{-1})	$\Delta k = k$ mixture - ($k_{HA_1} + k_{HA_2}$) $\times 10^2$
Acetic acid +	1.2 to 2.5	0.25 to 0.33	16.4 to 12.2
Benzoic acid	0.74 to 1.5		
Acetic acid +	1.2 to 2.5		
Phenyl acetic acid	0.53 to 0.90	0.12 to 0.18	3.6 to -1.03
Benzoic acid +	0.3 to 0.59		
Phenol	1.78 to 6.43	0.13 to 0.52	1.48 to 39.36
Acetic acid +	1.243		
Phenol	1.02 to 3.35	0.10 to 0.33	4.61 to 27.24
Phenylacetic acid +	0.1794		
Phenol	1.02 to 3.35	0.058 to 0.186	2.5 to 15.1

Our experiments with phenol differ from their work from the fact, that in their case, phenol when present alone, did not react with diazoacetic ester in benzene, whereas, in our case phenol reacts quite considerably with carbinol base. Since both the acids in the mixture react with carbinol base, it is difficult to distinguish the catalytic power of each individual acid or to say definitely whether the forward or the reverse reaction is being mutually affected. It is however likely from the high value of r that phenol strongly combines with the coloured salt formed and so makes the other acid more active by suppressing its reverse reaction.

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